

Synthesis and Reactions of Methoxy Methylene Ketones

(Km.) SHOBHA MISHRA and R. D. SHRIVASTAVA*

Holkar Science College, Indore.

Manuscript received 4 February 1975, revised 1 February 1978, accepted 4 April 1978

A convenient method for preparing methoxy methylene ketones $R-CO-C_R=CHOCH_3$ is described. Their properties and characterisation by preparation of derivatives are also described.

THE methyl ether (III, Alk=CH₃) of a hydroxy methylene ketone (II) which is the enol form of the 2-formyl ketone (I), is the methoxy methylene ketone.

The preparation of (III') or (III) is beset with difficulty. This is because the alkylation reaction which is carried out with an alkyl halide and (II) in presence of sodium ethoxide, gives in some cases the required O-alkyl ether (III) but in others the C-alkylation product namely 2-alkyl 2-formyl ketone (IV).

Thus whereas Bishop, Claisen and Sinclair¹ on treating hydroxymethylene camphor (V) with methyl iodide in presence of sodium ethoxide obtained the O-methyl ether of (V), Sen and Mondal² by working with hydroxymethylene cyclohexanone (VI) under similar conditions obtained 2-methyl 2-formyl cyclohexanone (VII)

Agarwal and Deshapande³ obtained the C-ethylation product corresponding to VIII, by treating (VI) with ethyl iodide, but by using n-amyl bromide in place of ethyl iodide they obtained the O-n-amyl ether of (VI)⁴.

* Deptt. of Chemistry, Government P. G. College, Neemuch.

Another difficulty in the preparation of the O-alkyl ethers, is their instability. R. Robinson and J. Walkar⁵ could prepare the desired O-methyl ether of (VI) by a method to be described presently. They state that the ether is unstable. It decomposes within a few minutes turning green. We have shown that if carefully purified the ether is fairly stable.

Their method was to dissolve (VI) in equivalent amount of aqueous caustic potash and then to add calculated amount of dimethylsulphate under mechanical stirring and extracting from the reaction mixture—the neutral O-methyl ether formed, by solvent ether.

We have improved upon this method by eliminating the preparations of the hydroxymethylene ketones but using in its place its sodium derivative which is directly obtainable by treating the parent ketone (in the present case cyclohexanone) with ethyl formate and metallic sodium. Another advantage of this technique is that hydroxymethylene ketones (II) such as hydroxymethylene acetone (II; R=CH₃, R'=H) which can not be isolated since they rapidly undergo self condensation to benzene derivatives^{6,7} can be methylated through their directly obtainable sodium derivative.

The use of sodium derivative in place of the hydroxymethylene ketone in the methylation experiments with dimethylsulphate, was first attempted by J. Walkar⁸ in the preparation of methyl ether of hydroxymethylene acetophenone (II; R=C₆H₅, R'=H). On isolation and distillation of the reaction product the O-methyl ether was obtained in poor yield, a large amount of tarry matter being produced.

This paper describes the experimental conditions under which a satisfactory yield of O-methyl ether of hydroxymethylene can be obtained.

The following methoxymethylene ketones are described. Those marked with an asterisk are prepared for the first time.

1. 1-methoxy-but-1-en-3-one III'
(R=CH₃, R'=H)*
2. 1-methoxy-2-methyl-but-1-en-3-one III'
(R=CH₃, R'=CH₃)*
3. 1-methoxy-2-methyl-pent-1-en-3-one III'
(R=C₂H₅, R'=CH₃)*
4. 1-methoxy-5-methyl-hex-1-en-3-one III'
(R=C₄H₉, R'=H)*
5. α-methoxy-γ-keto-γ-phenyl-α-propylene III'
(R=C₆H₅, R'=H)
6. 1-methoxy methylene cyclohexan-2-one
(O-methyl ether of VI)
7. 1-methoxymethylene-3-isopropyl-6-methyl
cyclohexan-2-one VIII*

In all cases the O-methylation was confirmed by estimation of OCH₃. In the case of α-hydroxy-γ-keto-γ-phenyl-α-propylene (II, R=C₆H₅, R'=H) a liquid acidic product in addition to the expected α-methoxy-γ-keto-γ-phenyl-α-propylene (III', R=C₆H₅, R'=H) was also obtained. This is different from the C-methylation product (IV', R=C₆H₅, R'=H) which must be identical with formyl propiophenone. The latter was synthesised by Claisen and Meyerowitz⁹ and is a crystalline solid m.p. 118°. The acidic methylation product is under investigation.

The methoxymethylene ketones are liquids and when carefully purified are fairly stable. They can be distilled under reduced pressure without decomposition. They are readily hydrolysed by cold aqueous alkali and to some extent even by water. This explains why they turn blue litmus red and give faint violet colour with ferric chloride. With semicarbazide they form the semicarbazone but most of them produce pyrazole derivatives. When warmed with concentrated hydrochloric acid, methyl chloride is evolved which burns with green bordered flame.

Experimental

The following procedure was, in general, adopted in the preparation of methoxymethylene ketones.

A solution in dry ether of parent ketone (1 mol) and ethyl formate (1.2 mol) was added in small instalments and with stirring, to pulverised sodium (1 atom) suspended in dry ether in a flask cooled in ice bath. In the course of about two hours the desired sodium derivative of the hydroxymethylene ketone was formed and was allowed to remain under ether overnight. After filtering off the sodium derivative under suction; washing with dry ether and drying on porous tile, it was weighed and dissolved in water.

A quantity of dimethyl sulphate previously purified by washing with cold dilute sodium carbonate followed by cold water, and in proportion somewhat less than theoretical, was then added in instalments and under mechanical stirring, to the solution of the sodium derivative of hydroxymethylene ketone. The flask containing the reaction mixture was kept in ice water, and cold caustic soda was added to the mixture if required to keep it slightly alkaline. The methoxy-methylene ketone which generally separated as a light liquid was extracted repeatedly with ether; the extracts washed with very dilute alkali followed by water, dried over calcium chloride and solvent distilled off. The residual liquid was then distilled under reduced pressure.

- (1) 1-methoxy-but-1-en-3-one (III', R=CH₃, R'=H)*

B. p. 75°/15 mm, yield 34% (Found: C, 59.7; H, 8.5; -OCH₃, 30.2, C₅H₈O₂ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0; -OCH₃, 31.0 percent). It is a pale yellow oil, lighter than water. It slowly dissolves in caustic soda solution and gives faint violet colour with aqueous ferric chloride. It is unstable and gradually darkens in colour. With semicarbazide it gives the pyrazole derivative, m.p. 230°, instead of the semicarbazone suggesting a prior hydrolysis. (Found: N, 34.0; C₆H₁₁O₂N₃ (semicarbazone) requires N, 26.7; C₅H₇ON₃ (Pyrazole) requires N, 33.3 percent).

- (2) 1-methoxy-2-methyl-but-1-en-3-one (III', R=CH₃, R'=CH₃) It is prepared by the same procedure described above in 55% yield, b.p. 85°/15mm.

(Found: C, 62.3; H, 8.0; O-CH₃, 28.0; C₆H₁₀O₂ requires C, 63.1; H, 8.7; OCH₃ 27.0 percent).

It is a clear pale yellow light liquid which dissolves slowly in excess of alkali. With semicarbazide gives the pyrazole m.p. 238°.

- (Found: N, 29.6; C₆H₉ON₃ requires N, 30.2 percent).

- (3) 1-methoxy-2-methyl-pent-1-en-3-one (III', R=C₂H₅, R'=CH₃)

Yield 40%. b.p. 115°/15 mm.

(Found: C, 64.5; H, 9.4; OCH₃, 23.2; C₇H₁₂O₂ requires C, 65.0; H, 9.7; OCH₃, 24.0 percent). It is insoluble in water and only very slowly dissolves in excess alkali. It is quite stable.

- (4) 1-methoxy-5-methyl-hex-1-en-3-one (III', R=C₄H₉, R'=H)

Yield 35%. b.p. 100°/15 mm.

(Found: C, 68.1; H, 10.1; OCH₃, 21.9; C₈H₁₄O₂ requires: C, 67.6; H, 10.0; OCH₃, 21.7 percent).

It is insoluble in water but gives violet colour with aqueous ferric chloride. It is quite stable. With semicarbazide it forms a pyrazole derivative m.p. 237°.

(Found : N, 26.0 ; $C_8H_{13}ON_3$ requires N, 27.0 percent).

(5) α -methoxy- γ -keto- γ -phenyl- α -propylene (III', $R=C_6H_5$, $R'=H$)

Yield 33%. b.p. 110°/15 mm.

(Found : C, 73.2 ; H, 6.2 ; OCH_3 , 19.0 ; $C_{10}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 74.0 ; H, 6.7 ; OCH_3 , 19.4 percent). It is a light yellow liquid which dissolves slowly in excess of dilute alkali. It forms a semicarbazone m.p. 163°.

(Found : N, 19.2 ; $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N_3$ requires N, 19.1 percent). Walkar⁸ who had previously prepared this methyl ether but did not characterise it by the preparation of any derivative mentions that it distills at 145° - 147°/12 mm.

(6) 1-methoxymethylene cyclohexan-2-one (O-methylether of VI)

Yield 40%. b.p. 92°/15 mm.

(Found : C, 68.0 ; H, 8.4 ; OCH_3 , 20.8 ; $C_8H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 68.5 ; H, 8.5 ; OCH_3 , 22.0 percent). It is a stable compound which forms semicarbazone m.p. 22.0°.

(Found : N, 20.1 ; $C_9H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 21.0 percent).

(7) 1-methoxymethylene-3-isopropyl-6-methylcyclohexan-2-one (VIII). This preparation was difficult and was obtained in poor yield. It was difficult to purify it. Its OCH_3 content was found to be 12.2 when it should be 15.8 percent. It reacts with semicarbazide but the reaction products proved to be a mixture.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to late Dr. S. S. Deshpande for his keen interest and guidance. One of us (SM) thanks CSIR for the award of Junior fellowship.

References

1. A. BISHOP, L. CLAISEN and W. SINCLAIR, *Ann.* 1894, 281, 366.
2. H. K. SEN and K. MONDAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1928, 9, 627.
3. R. R. AGARWAL and S. S. DESHPANDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1949, 26, 183.
4. R. R. AGARWAL and S. S. DESHPANDE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1951, 28, 65.
5. R. ROBINSON and J. WALKER, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1935, 1530.
6. L. CLAISEN and L. STYLOS, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1145.
7. L. CLAISEN, *Ann.* 1894, 281, 307.
8. J. WALKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 130.
9. L. CLAISEN and L. MEYEROWITZ, *Ber.*, 1889, 22, 3277.